

Guidelines for Creating SSHOC-NL Tutorials

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1. Goal of document

This document contains the guidelines to develop educational resources for the CLARIAH-NL Teaching and Training programme. Researchers that are part of CLARIAH-NL and the overall SSHOC-NL consortium are invited to develop resources following the guidelines in this document to disseminate their work, optimise the user experience of the infrastructure and contribute to training of students and researchers in the Netherlands and abroad. The document builds upon the original CLARIAH Learn document “Guidelines for making Media Suite Tutorials”, which have been adjusted to suit both the wider interdisciplinary scope of CLARIAH within SSHOC-NL and stimulate collaboration between CLARIAH and ODDISEI within the consortium. These practical guidelines are connected to the background document “Strategy Report Teaching & Training SSHOC-NL (5.2)” in which the overall education strategy for task 5.2 has been set out. In these guidelines, the goals of the tutorials, their general structure and format, metadata and distribution are set out so uniform resources can be disseminated. It is not necessary to read the strategy document before following the guidelines, but it may be helpful for context.

2. Aims for SSHOC-NL Tutorials

The aim for the SSHOC-NL tutorials is threefold. Firstly, through providing step-by-step instructions, the tutorials facilitate use of the infrastructure and the tools and resources (digital collections and datasets) it makes available to researchers, teachers and students.

Secondly, educational resources such as tutorials are a way to bridge the back-end focus with the front-end user experience. This means that developers can provide examples of possible applications and use cases of the infrastructure and its tools. Lastly, it is a way to contribute to the foundation of the CLARIAH-NL and overall SSHOC-NL community. The intended demographic for these resources are researchers that wish to use the infrastructure or implement the tools, collections and datasets in their research, teachers implementing these in their classroom and university students from BA to RMA level that wish to use the tools in relation to their course work.

There are different types of resources set out in this document.

- **Written tutorials**

- Explanatory tutorials: These are broad, general and can be implemented in different disciplines and curricula. They centre around the explanation of tools, specific datasets, collections or overall infrastructure and include reflection questions (e.g. this [tutorial](#)).
- Methodological tutorials: These are domain specific and elaborate upon specific methodology. They include examples of particular research that can be carried out or the way that tools and functionalities can be implemented and also contain reflection questions (e.g. this [tutorial](#)).
- Workflows: Workflows summarise the different steps a user has to take to get to a specific result. Compared to tutorials, they are more concrete, shorter and leave out contextualising information, reflection and examples. They are most suitable for explaining how to use tools and infrastructures, and include less tool or data criticism. Workflows were not part of the original CLARIAH Learn strategy but will be implemented in CLARIAH-NL Teaching and Training programme. This format can be used for specific use cases that tasks might want to highlight. Workflow examples can be found through the [SSH Open Marketplace](#).

- **Example Projects**

- These can exist of fellowship projects, for example through the publication of a project description and where possible deliverables. (e.g. this [example project](#))
- They can also exist as a combination of a tutorial and a lecturer's manual, ready to be implemented into the classroom. (e.g. [this example project](#))
- This format can also be used to highlight specific use cases of tools and infrastructure, where tasks want to provide more context than a workflow format allows and provide less of a manual than the tutorial format. In this case, the exact format can be determined depending on the project.

- **Video tutorial**

- Video tutorials can be developed in support of written tutorials. This can be in the form of a short video, for example under a minute, primarily to illustrate

how specific functionalities work. They can also be created in the form of a longer video that discusses several of the steps of the tutorial.

3. Tutorial content and format

3.1 Written Tutorial

Tutorial

The written tutorial format can be either an explanatory or a methodological tutorial or take the shape of a workflow. All three follow the same formats, although workflows are considerably shorter and serve to be more of a 'How to' reference than a step-by-step guide. While other formats are possible, it is important that the elements, format and style remain similar and recognizable and clearly associated with SSHOC-NL, CLARIAH or ODISSEI.

The tutorials will address different levels of expertise, and it will be indicated on which level the resource addresses research and learning (introductory, intermediate or advanced level). The tutorials take on a modular approach, meaning that single tutorials can be implemented in a classroom or workshop, but that multiple tutorials can also be combined into a large exercise. This allows users to build complex knowledge and skills step-wise and cover the steps or workflow of a specific type of analysis or research comprehensively. It is very much encouraged to provide tutorials in multiple languages where possible, to serve the international SSHOC-NL community. Moreover, to improve shareability and modularity, we also encourage makers of a tutorial to make use of and indicate a creative commons license, although this is not required.

It is also possible to make a distinction within one tutorial into basic and advanced steps but it is always necessary for the individual components to complement each other (e.g. this [example project](#)). Explanatory and methodological tutorials can ideally be completed within 30-45 minutes. This length makes it possible to integrate the module within an existing course. Please ensure the written tutorials are in PDF-format, and when possible, run the final draft by task 5.2 (Christian Olesen or Mary-Joy van der Deure).

Tutorials should include the following elements:

1. Front page:

- **Tutorial title:** Give the tutorial a title, beginning with 'SSHOC-NL Tutorial' followed by the functionalities and type of research discussed.
 - For example: 'SSHOC-NL Tutorial: Searching and Exploring Climate Narratives Within and Across Datasets'.

- **Tutorial Subtitle:** Add a subtitle below the title that mentions the author(s) of the tutorial, their affiliated institutes, as well as the month and year of publication.
 - For example: 'Tutorial made by Mary-Joy van der Deure, University of Amsterdam, January 2026'
- **Image:** Add a screenshot to the front page that reflects the tutorial's content.

2. After the front page, the tutorial needs to contain the following sections (See [this tutorial](#) as an example):

- **Tutorial Description, Case and Objective:** On page two, the tutorial needs to begin with a section that describes the content, the cases or examples discussed, and the objectives of the tutorial. See [this tutorial](#) as an example. Please approach this from a learner's perspective and describe relevant aspects such as time investment and the goals the participant will achieve after following the tutorial.
- **Types and levels of teaching and research:** This section should state which types of teaching and research the tutorial fits into and which level of users it addresses. Here, it should mention if the tutorial is suited for an introductory, intermediate or advanced level
- **Prerequisites:** This section should indicate which steps are necessary to have taken, before following the tutorial. Here, it should also mention if this is a basic or advanced tutorial, or where additional relevant documents can be found.
- **Acknowledgements (optional):** Depending on the research you describe, you may need to include acknowledgements, for instance in case funding has been received or if you have received input from colleagues.
- **Steps:** After the introductory sections above, the steps to be followed make up most of the tutorial. Begin these steps on a new page. All steps are numbered, and each step should begin with a screenshot that illustrates the key aspect of that particular step.
- **References (Optional):** In case texts or other resources have been cited, make sure to include a list of resources at the end of the document using the 18th edition of the Chicago Manual of Style (Author-Date).

Lecturer's Manual

The lecturer's manuals are accompanying documents to the written tutorials. They are more summarizing, and do not require any information on objectives or prerequisites or front page in general. For an example, see [this manual](#).

- **Title:** Clearly state that the document is a lecturer's manual, and in the subtitle below state which tutorial the document accompanies.
 - For example: 'SSHOC-NL Lecturer's Manual. Tutorial: Creating a Data Visualization with Google Sheets and the Media Suite'.
- **Tutorial Subtitle:** Add a subtitle below the title that mentions the author(s) of the tutorial, their affiliated institutes, as well as the month and year of publication.
 - For example: 'Tutorial made by Mary-Joy van der Deure, University of Amsterdam, January 2026'

- **Description:** Provide a short description on the contents of the Lecturer’s manual. Elaborate on the contexts in which the tutorial can be given, such as an in-class discussion or workshops.
- **Steps:** The manual should follow the same steps as the tutorial. For each step:
 - Summarize what the step entails and what the participants will do.
 - Provide answers to any questions asked in the tutorial (e.g. results that they might find)
 - Provide possible points of attention to any reflection questions being asked in the tutorial (e.g. what can be brought up in discussion or what answers the participants might give)
- Keep this document brief. It is intended to be a practical manual to keep beside the original tutorial. It is recommended to upload both files together on Zenodo or other distribution platforms, so they can be downloaded as a bundle.

Workflow

Workflows are considerably shorter than regular tutorials, and are meant to provide a quick overview that explains how to use specific tools or infrastructure, without the critical reflection that is part of a tutorial. See [this SSH Open Marketplace workflow](#) as an example.

- **Title:** Add a title and state the workflow topic.
- **Subtitle:** Add a subtitle with the name of the author(s), the affiliated institutions and the month and year of publication.
- **Description:** Add a short description of the workflow, preferably not more than one paragraph. Describe the activity that the workflow addresses as well as the tool or infrastructure in which it can be used. Link to the infrastructures or tools through hyperlinks where possible. Add additional context if necessary for the topic.
- **Steps:** As short as possible, describe the steps in the workflow. This can range from two to three sentences per step, to a very short paragraph.
- **Images:** Where possible and relevant, add an illustration of the workflow to visualise the different steps.

Example project

Example projects consist of either multiple resources distributed together (e.g. [this example](#)), a tutorial accompanied by a lecturer’s manual (such as [here](#)) or a use case that requires a different format than previously mentioned. The structure can follow the description above, as long as all resources are distributed together as one project.

3.2 Style Sheet of written resources

The text of the written resources should be formatted according to the following style sheet:

- **Font:** Maven Pro
- Tutorial title: Size 26, title case, bold.

- Screenshot, front page: the width should be 5.5, the height is variable, and a 2pt image border should be added to the image.
- **Tutorial headings 2:** Size 18, title case, bold
- **Tutorial headings 3:** Size 12, sentence case, bold
- **Regular text:** Size 12
- **In-text images:** Aim for a width of 6.5 but variable if need be, height is variable depending on example.

3.3 Video Tutorial

Video tutorials are meant to complement the written tutorials and may be embedded in written tutorials where relevant. They can be of a short duration, for example less than a minute, and illustrate how a particular functionality works. The video tutorial may also be longer, and discuss several of the steps of the written tutorial, in which case a length of 5-7 minutes is recommended. Ideally, a video tutorial should not be longer than 10 minutes. If more time is needed, it is recommended that the video tutorials become a series, such as in [this example](#). Please use the logo of the CLARIAH project in the introduction. The rest of the video style is flexible, and can be personalised. The tutorial can contain an explanatory voice-over, or only include screen recordings. The video can include music, but does not have to. Please make sure the video does not contain any copyright-protected materials.

4. Metadata

It is important to add the right metadata to your educational resource, to ensure proper distribution and enhance findability. It is strongly recommended to upload resources to [Zenodo](#), and to follow these metadata fields. This way, a proper overview of all SSHOC-NL educational resources will be created. Additionally, however, it is important to adjust the metadata to the other platforms of distribution where relevant and needed.

For Zenodo, add the following metadata:

- The full title of the resource
- Publication date
- The type of resource (e.g. 'lesson')
- The authors of the resource, use their ORCID ID where possible
- The description of the resource
 - Describe the content of the resource as well as its format (e.g. tutorial or workflow).
 - Describe possible theoretical perspectives present in the resource
 - When relevant, mention the (inter)disciplinary perspective of the resource

- Describe the tutorial also from a learning experience, add the time investment it requires, the level of research or learning or specific prerequisites there might be.
- The right Creative Commons licence
- The keywords that describe the resources
- The language of the resource
- The date of publication
- DOI identifier
- Feel free to fill in any other metadata field that might be relevant to your resource.

For uploads on Zenodo, please **make sure to add the resource to the CLARIAH (or ODISSEI) community**. This ensures a proper overview of all project resources. You can do so by going to the resource after publication, and click on the 'gear icon' in 'Communities'. Here you can select 'Submit to a community' and search for either project. Your resource will be approved before being visible in the community.

Besides Zenodo, it is important to **follow the metadata of the platform you are distributing your resources**. SSH Open Marketplace, for example, includes 'activities', meaning the tasks you can perform using the resource or intended audience. For a full list of SSH Open Marketplace metadata and vocabulary, see [here](#).

5. Distribution

It is highly recommended to upload all resources to Zenodo. In doing so, the CLARIAH and ODISSEI communities will build an overview of all resources through which users can browse and search. Additionally, it is up to the author of the resource where to distribute. Please see the strategy document for a more complete overview of the current educational landscape and different options. Task 5.2 recommends the following platforms for distribution

- [SSH Open Marketplace](#): The discovery portal for both the social sciences and the humanities. It pays specific attention to the entire research cycle, and includes tools, datasets, training materials and workflows that users can search through. It offers a large variety of resources and extensive metadata and is very suitable to distribute all types of educational resources.
- [Edusources](#): This platform is directed at higher education resources in the Netherlands. It is easy to navigate the large collection of open access resources in both Dutch and English. It is a suitable platform to disseminate tutorials and lecturer's manuals, although it is less directed at research, meaning it is less suitable for infrastructure specific workflows or use cases without educational reflection.

- [Github](#): Lastly, educational resources can be uploaded to Github. Specifically more technical workflows, datasets and documents can be uploaded here. See, for example, the [CLARIAH Tool Discovery page](#).

Authors are free to choose different platforms to disseminate their resources. Additionally, task 5.2 encourages the transformation of tutorials and workflows into in-person workshops, and can assist in this transformation and organisation.

For any further questions, please contact Christian Olesen or Mary-Joy van der Deure (University of Amsterdam).